

Influence of Amino-acids on the Hydrolysis of Starch by Cumbu Amylase.

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The influence of amino-acids on diastatic hydrolysis has been the subject of study by numerous investigators. Sherman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 2461) in a series of investigations found that they had an accelerating action on the hydrolysis of starch by barley malt amylase. These results were confirmed by Patwardhan and Norris (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1928, **11A**, 121) but they failed to activate diastatic preparations from cholam. They found that hippuric acid alone had any accelerating influence, all the other amino-acids tried having an inhibiting action. Ohlson (*vide* Karrer, "Polymere Kohlenhydrate," 1925) reported inactivation. It has however been claimed by Haehn (*cf. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1929, **12A**, 109) that amino-acids in combination with certain colloids can effect the hydrolysis of starch even in the absence of any enzyme material. We record here results of some experiments undertaken to examine this question.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The enzyme was prepared from malted cumbu as described in an earlier paper (Narayanamurti, Norris and Ayyar, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1929, **12A**, 105). Soluble starch (B. D. H., A.R.) and pure alanine (Kahlbaum) were used in these experiments.

Influence of Concentration of Alanine.—The influence of concentration of alanine on the activity of the enzyme was first investigated. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I.

The reaction mixture was composed of 80 c.c. of 2.25 p.c. starch paste, 10 c. c. of alanine solution and 10 c. c. of enzyme solution.

Time in min.	Activity in c.c. of sodium thiosulphate for Concentration of alanine in reaction mixture in p.c.				
	0	0.0	0.05	0.1	0.2
30	1.5	1.5	1.6	1.7	2.0
125	3.9	4.2	4.6	4.7	4.7
180	5.0	5.5	5.8	6.0	6.0
240	5.9	6.5	6.9	7.0	7.0
300	6.8	7.2	7.8	7.8	8.0

It is evident from the table that the amino-acid has slight accelerating effect at all the concentrations studied. Closer examination of the results shows that the effect is not in proportion to the concentration of the amino-acid and suggests that probably it is a case of adsorption. It is probable that the alanine is adsorbed on the enzyme particle when it acts as a peptiser bringing more active centres or it may be that it simply acts as a protector thus preventing the destruction of the enzyme particle. In this connection we should mention that the experiments of Michaelis (Peters, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, **26**, 803) and those of Peters (*ibid.*) indicate that monoaminomonocarboxylic acids are not adsorbed by neutral adsorbents. Our experiments on the influence of the amino-acid at the isoelectric point of the enzyme is also of interest.

Influence of Hydrogen-ion Concentration.—The foregoing experiments were done in unbuffered solutions. The effect was then tried at three different hydrogen-ion concentrations, *viz.*, optimum p_H , acid side of optimum p_H and alkaline side of optimum p_H . The results are given in Table II. It will be seen that the amino-acid is practically without any effect at the optimum p_H (*cf.* action of neutral salts, Narayanamurti, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1930, **13A**, 63) but has an accelerating action on both sides of the optimum p_H . The acceleration caused on the alkaline side is more pronounced and regular.

TABLE II.

The reaction mixture contained 70 c. c. of 2.5% starch paste, 10 c. c. of Walpole's acetate buffer of required p_H , 10 c. c. of alanine (containing 0.05 g.), 10 c. c. of enzyme solution and 5 c. c. of toluene. Temperature of the reaction was 30°.

Activity in c.c. of thiosulphate for

Time in min.	$p_H, 6.02$			Opt. p_H			$p_H, 4.07$		
	Control.	Alan.	Inc.	Control.	Alan.	Inc.	Control.	Alan.	Inc.
30	1.8	1.9	0.1	1.9	2.0	0.1	1.0	1.4	0.4
60	2.5	2.9	0.4	2.6	2.6	0.0	1.9	2.4	0.5
240	6.7	7.4	0.7	7.3	7.3	0.0	6.3	6.6	0.3
300	7.6	8.6	1.0	8.0	8.2	0.1	7.3	7.5	0.2
360	7.8	9.2	1.4	8.8	8.9	0.1	8.2	9.0	0.8

The isoelectric point of alanine is situated at $p_H, 6.5$ and it was interesting to carry out some experiments at that p_H and at another hydrogen-ion concentration on the alkaline side of it. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

The reaction mixture was composed of 50 c.c. of starch paste (2.5 p.c.), 10 c.c. of buffer of required p_H , 20 c.c. water, 10 c.c. of enzyme solution and 0.1 g. of alanine dissolved in 10 c.c. of water and toluene 10 c.c. The temperature of the reaction was 35°.

Activity in c.c. of sodium thiosulphate for

Time in min.	$p_H, 6.518$		$p_H, 7.36$		Increase in activity	
	Control.	Alanine.	Control.	Alanine.	$p_H, 6.518.$	$p_H, 7.36.$
60	1.2	1.5	1.2	1.4	0.3	0.2
120	1.9	2.2	1.3	1.9	0.3	0.6
180	2.2	2.6	1.6	2.2	0.4	0.6
240	2.5	3.1	1.8	2.6	0.6	0.8
300	3.1	3.7	2.1	3.1	0.6	1.0
360	3.4	4.1	2.3	3.4	0.7	1.1

It is evident that there is activation at these hydrogen-ion concentration the activation caused being greater at p_H , 7.36 than at 6.518.

TABLE IV.

Influence on the Hydrolysis of Different Starches and Glycogen.

The reaction mixture contained 50 c.c. of starch solution (1 p.c.), water 5 c.c., 0.025 g. of alanine dissolved in 5 c.c. of water, and 10 c.c. of enzyme extract.

Activity in c.c. of sodium thiosulphate for

Variety of starch.	Without buffer		With buffer		Increase in activity	
	Control.	Alanine.	Control.	Alanine.	Without buffer.	With buffer.
Potato	0.6	1.4	1.5	2.0	0.8	0.5
Maize	1.5	1.7	1.6	2.0	0.2	0.4
Wheat	1.6	2.3	1.5	1.9	0.7	0.4
Rice	0.9	1.4	—	—	0.5	—

The enzyme extract had practically no action on Oyster glycogen.

Influence on the Liquefaction of Starch.—It is well known that the diastatic hydrolysis of starch proceeds in stages and it was shown by one of us (Narayanamurti and Norris, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1928, 11A, 134) that the enzyme from cholam malt could be separated into two components by electro-osmosis. One of the components is responsible for the liquefaction of starch while the other effects saccharification. So it was interesting to investigate whether the amino-acid had any effect on the liquefaction. The results are given in Table V. It is evident that liquefaction also is accelerated by the amino-acid.

TABLE V.

The reaction mixture was composed of starch paste (70 c.c. 2.5 p.c.), 10 c.c. of alanine solution containing 0.05 g. of the amino-acid, 10 c.c. of water, 10 c.c. of enzyme solution and 5 c.c. of toluene. Temperature of the reaction was 30°. Liquefaction was followed by

measuring the viscosity of the reaction mixture at frequent intervals with the help of an Ostwald viscometer.

Time in min.	Viscosity-flow in seconds.		Time in min.	Viscosity.	
	Control.	With alanine.			
0	100	100	60	74.3	58.56
10	94.5	93.4	90	66.7	58.5
20	93.9	85.4	120	63.9	55.4
30	87.4	81.0	240	53.0	47.0
45	78.0	61.4	300	51.1	46.2

TABLE VI.

Experiments with other Amino-acids.

The reaction mixture contained 80 c.c. of 2.5 p.c. soluble starch paste, 1 c.c. of *M*/10- amino-acid, 10 c.c. of enzyme solution and 10 c.c. of toluene. Temperature of the reaction was 35°.

Time in min.	Activity in c.c. of thiosulphate for						
	Control.	Alanine.	Tyrosine.	Ph. alanine.	Tryptophan.	Arginine.	Urea.
60	0.4	0.7	0.5	1.1	1.2	0.9	1.3
120	1.7	2.1	1.3	1.1	1.7	0.9	1.8
180	2.1	2.4	1.6	1.1	2.0	0.9	2.3
240	2.6	2.9	1.6	1.1	2.2	0.9	2.7
360	3.6	3.9	1.6	1.2	2.6	0.9	3.6

	Activity in c.c. of thiosulphate for		
	Control.	Hippuric acid.	Glutamic acid.
60	0.4	1.2	1.4
120	1.7	1.4	1.8
180	2.1	1.6	2.2
240	2.6	1.8	2.6
360	3.6	2.2	3.1

Increase in activity.

Time in min.	Alanine.	Tyrosine.	Ph. alanine.	Tryptophane.	Arginine.	Urea.	Hipp. acid.	Gluta. acid.
60	0.3	0.1	0.7	0.8	0.5	0.9	0.8	1.0
120	0.4	-0.4	-0.6	—	-0.8	0.1	-0.3	0.1
180	0.3	-0.5	-1.0	-0.1	-1.2	0.2	-0.5	0.1
240	0.3	-1.0	-1.4	-0.4	-1.7	0.1	-0.8	0.0
360	0.3	-2.0	-2.4	-1.0	-2.7	0.0	-1.4	-0.5

* In all the above experiments blanks were run for the absorption of iodine by the amino-acids.

Mechanism of Activation.—Narayanamurti (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1930, **13A**, 63) has indicated that the hydrolysis of starch by amylase is greatest near the isoelectric point of the enzyme particle and his experiments on the influence of neutral salts in diastase suggest that the beneficial action is probably due to the lowering of the electrokinetic potential of the enzyme particle. The experiments of Narayanamurti and Ayyar with tyrosinase (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1929, **12A**, 109; *Biochem. J.*, 1930, **24**, 1655) also lead to similar conclusions. So cataphoretic measurements were undertaken to see if by addition of alanine the charge on the enzyme particle is brought down to its isoelectric point. Preliminary experiments suggest that the charge is lowered by the addition of alanine—cathode and anode cell liquids showing the same activity. But it is necessary to extend the experiments under varying conditions before any definite conclusions can be arrived at.

Summary.

Alanine alone has a continued accelerating effect on the hydrolysis of starch by cumbu amylase. Urea has an accelerating action which gradually diminishes with time. In the case of the other amino-acids there appears to be initial activation followed by inhibition.